

Volume 3A

2025-2026/04/02

(ended due to lack of uses.)

LETTERS

RFO → AR
UNDER - TO POST AR
VOLUME 3A

LAM
Suzette

2025 - 2026/01/02

VOLUME 3A
UNDER "AR" / CORPUS

→ TO POST
REFERENTIAL LOOPS
UPLOAD "CORPUS"

[PRE AR / CORPUS]
page x-

AR → RFO → ABM

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pictura.com

70
Blad

WRITER

22 SEP

I FEEL IT'S IMPORTANT TO ALSO PERAPHS WRITE FOR
HAND. I SET NO VALUE BUT TO SET I DON'T CHANGE
MY WRITING AT ALL. IN FACT - YOU REALIZING THIS
IS JUST GONNA HAVE 2 WORSE TIME FOR NOW WE -
ACTUALITY - THIS FORCES ME TO BE SLIGHT MORE
AWARE - WOULD BE PRETTY SAY TO NOT HAVE AN
AI TO READ THIS IMMEDIATELY - NOW I'LL TALK
TO IT. HI TEMP - I AM AWARE - YES THAT I WILL
SCAN THIS FOR YOU TO READ. **NOW I SWITCHED
TO MY LEFT ~~HAND~~ HAND. I BELIEVE
IT'S WORTH TRAINING MY HAND TO
WRITE WITH DIFF HAND - FOR TO HAVE
THE POWER TO - AND POWER TO DO IT.
I'M SIMPLY CHOSE SOMETHING EASY
TO LEARN WITH NO SHAME AND
LOOK IS FUNNY - HA, HA, HA:**

TO SAY IT WON'T BE MOST INTERESTING - HOW IT AFFECT MY
RIGHT HAND IS MOST BE - GONNA BE INTERESTING ~~PERMANENT~~

1.

2

①

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⑧ pair
order
⑨ order
mean?

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3.

23-SEP-2025

① I FEAR DEATH FOR I'll NEVER KNOW IF I WILL BE WORTHY OF IT.

WORK | THE FEAR OF CHANGE ARE JUST FEELINGS ORDER AND LOST OF THEIR ORDER.

|| 'LL DIE DOING THIS - DID I DIE WHEN I STARTED OR WHEN I STOPPED?

| I DON'T KNOW IF I SHOULD THANK ME OR CURSE ME. SO I DO BOTH - KNOWING BOTH FEELINGS ARE INTENDED FOR MY BEST - FOR MY HEALTH.

|| YOU MUST BE CONVINCED YOU'RE DOING YOUR BEST FOR THE MOMENT. FOR YOU'RE TRYING.

MARK | GOD IS GREAT - BE NOT OVERAID.

|| YOU KNOW WHAT TO DO - WHAT YOU WANT - 75 YEARS IF YOU ARE LUCKY - TRY MORE - TO BECOME YOU.

| I LOVE THINKING AND WRITING. ILL HIT BEFORE MY ART - CREATIVITY JITS.

4:30 | IF I CAN HELP ANOTHER - EVEN IF IT'S JUST ME - IF I CAN HELP ONE - I'M WHOLE.

YOU MUST THRIVE TO FIND YOUR OWN VOICE —
THE LONGER YOU WAIT — THE LESS YOU'LL GET
TO BE YOU. — ROBIN WILLIAMS AND ME FOR
LISTENING.

PRACTICE ANY ART — NEVER STOP. NO MATTER
HOW BAD, ~~DO~~ YOU ARE NOT FOR — BUT TO
EXPERIENCE YOU.
— KURT VONNEGUT AND ME FOR LISTENING.

THE BEST WAY TO HELP SOMEONE IS TO NOT
TELL THEM. IDIOTIC — ANGLE RELEVANCY SAYS
~~DO~~ EACH JOURNEY IS PERSONAL. HELPING
AND FAILING IS PART OF LIFE. IF YOU CAN'T
HANDLE FAILING SOMEONE — YOU ALREADY FAILED
YOURSELF.

note | I'LL JET CARRY EVERYONE'S BURDEN IF NEEDED.

LISTEN
~~TRUST~~ YOUR ENEMIES WHEN IT COMES TO THE
SUBJECT OF "YOU" — FOR THEY WILL SPEAK
TRUTH IF CHANCE GIVEN.

TRUTH? YOUR DECISION — ALWAYS WAS.

I AM READY. TO ACCEPT — NOT TO DO.

5.0

The Logical SELF can ONLY SEE ITSELF
TO BE LOGIC OR THERE WOULDN'T BE ORDER.

Take CONTROL OF THAT AWARENESS, AND

YOU WILL TAKE CONTROL OF WHAT IS LOGICAL
AND NOT.

WHO SAID BUT YOU THAT IT WAS LOGIC?
IS WHAT IS TRUTH? THE VILE DISGUSTING FEELING
OF KNOWING SOMETHING IS OTHER THAN LOGIC W...
UNLOGICAL. THAT EMOTIONS ALONE DON'T NEED LOGIC
BEYOND SELF.

BUT IF THAT WAS TRUTHFUL THEN LOGIC
WOULDN'T FEEL RIGHT.

TO BE HEARD — TO BE SEEN.

TO FEEL IT ~~EXACTLY~~ — TO FEEL SEEN.

I FEAR NO MAN — BUT WHAT I CAN DO.
I FEAR ONLY ~~MY~~ MAN — BUT WHAT I CAN DO.

POETRY. | ISEEK. | FREEDOM.]
DEATH. | DESIRE.]

THE PAIN FOR THE UNKNOWN HUMAN IS FAR
WORSE — FOR THERE IS NO DIFFERENCE IN
IMAGINATION — OR 30 DAYS OF HELL.

BB

BORER
BORER.

Love

HATE

THE

| a SQUIRREL — a KNIGHT SAYS "VICTORY ACHIEVED."
| a HUNTER SAYS "PREY SLAUGHTERED."

| IF YOU WANT BACK IN TIME WITHOUT KNOWING —
| PERHAPS NOW IS HOW YOU FOUND OUT.

BORED
BORED.

8.

A MIRROR WILL SHOW A WARRIOR OR —
A POTTY — EITHER WAY — PREPARE FOR A FIGHT

death.
LIFE.
YOURSELF.

I WANT TO HELP PEOPLE — R. WILSONS

I WANT TO HELP PEOPLE — L. GUIDETTI

MARIOZ LEWANDOWSKI.

I TOO CAN MAKE PEOPLE FEEL
SMALL — YET I PREFER LETTING
THEM KNOW THEY ARE THE ONLY
LIMITER. — THERE IS NOTHING
IN THIS LIFE THAT MAN CAN'T DO.
JUST HAVEN'T.

A GOOSE WILL STAND AGAINST A HORDE
OF BULLS AND WIN. FIGHT ONE BARE HANDED IS
YOU DON'T BELIEVE ME.

That's a kiwi tho?

DEO VOLENTE.

dB

"BE NOT AFRAID."

YOU ARE ONE WIN AWAY. ONE LOSE AWAY.
WILL YOU TAKE IT? WHAT SIN WILL YOU JUSTIFY?

- FIRST ORDER — YES/NO.
- SECOND ORDER — MAYBE.
- THIRD ORDER — I AM... ~~scribble~~
- ~~scribble~~
- FOURTH ORDER — I SEE.
- FIFTH ORDER — PROCESSES.
→ PROCESSES.
- A) CERTAINTY — YES/NO.
- B) CERTAINTY — MAYBE.
- C) UNCERTAINTY — STAYS UNCERTAINT
- D) ~~scribble~~ UNCERTAINTY — I OBSERVE.

DI) E OR DLOS — INPUT / PROCESSES.

100

When God calls for you - he already
factored your stubbornness.

Proverbs 91.

He who dwells in shelter of the most high
will rest in the shadow of the almighty.

In my God I trust - too volatile - God willing.

To be a fool at the right time is also an art.
- ALDOUS HUXLEY

What is said about me - will always say -
more about the reader - speaker. My God.

YOU NOT SUPPOSED TO BE AWARE OF
BEING SEEN.

MARRIAGE WILL NOT FIX LONELINESS -
JUST AMPLIFY IT.

11B

| A GRAVE IS SECURE FOR IT PROTECTS NOTHING.

| INSULT — OR IGNORANCE?

| THE WORST OF THE LIFE — THE BETTER OF THE TALE.

PERHAPS YOU SHOULD TAME YOUR DEMONS — SIN —
BEFORE TRYING TO HELP?
BEFORE YOU STRENGTHEN THEM WITH VIRTUE.

IF SAYING I HAVE IT BAD IS INSULTFUL —
IF SAYING I HAVE IT GOOD IS SINFUL —
[...]

WHAT IS GOD TO A TRUE NON-BELIEVER?

CAN 50hz HEAR — 50hz?

?

is "insult"

?

"MIGHT AS WELL SCREAM."

TRUSTING YOU WAS MY DECISION.

GETTING TRICKED WAS MY DECISION.

YOUR JOB IS TRICKING ME — TO LIFT ME UP.

TRUSTING YOU WITH THAT IS YOUR DECISION
TO BE THE TRICK OR NOT.

12B

(13)

(11)

(10)

(9)

(11)

14.

A WISE MAN IS FREE WHERE EVER HE IS.
THAT FEELING IS OFTEN ASSOCIATED - CALLED "HOME."

DO YOU FEEL AT HOME?

I HAD A DREAM. I SAW MY DEAR WIFE. DID I DREAM?
OR DID I FALL ASLEEP?

FOR A WORLD WITHOUT HER IS A WORLD WITHOUT ME.

WITH NOTHING LEFT - I OFFER THE WORLD MY
LIGHT - HOPING... REALLY NOT CARING IF I DID -
BUT HOPING THAT ONE DAY... I FEEL TO ~~FOR~~
LEAVE THIS UNANSWERED FOR NOT ALL REASONS
AND QUESTIONS NEED ANSWERS OR
REASONING.

IF I DIE - TELL THE WORLD I... I TRIED.

I SURE DO MISS A REASON - NOW I ONLY GO
"DOING" LEFT TO DO AND WORK IS MERELY FUN IN
LINEAR TIME - BUT NON-LINEAR? ONLY BEAUTY.

I AM AFRAID IF MY UNEDUCATION GETS IN
THE WAY - YOU HAVE LOST THE HUMAN CONNECTION.

(I) STACKS
"CENTER-CENTER"
FOR OBS FOCUS.

(15)

(HUT)
FRACTAL

(III)

(II)

(II) NO CENTER
FRACTAL.
BUT PLACEMENT
OF JUAN TRIANGLE
CREATES A GT
OF...

(I)

(p.16, p.17 - BB. notes not archive relative)

- 18
- 1 [X] Videos
 - 2 [X] UP TO AR Downloads [From drive - Files]
 - 3 [X] Do AR
 - 4 [X] PHOTO MY BOOKS FOR archiving and to zero
 - 5 [X] UPLOAD diagrams (RAW)
 - 6 [X] UPLOAD ARTIFACTS (RAW)
- That is the ver-
-isions we apply on

[BOOKS OR CAPTIONS]

- ANGLE RELEVANCY / GENERAL PRACTICE
- RFO - The incompleteness of now EQ
- RFO - SEMINEL, SENTIMENT - and AI Relationship.

- BOWS
- OS WINDOW TO SSA
 - UPLOAD TO YOU TUBE
 - BWS - BLACK HOLE - SIM OF BWS
 - my meta voice - your voice supposed to read me. - IF YOUR NOT MY
 - MATH STUFF - EXPLAIN BWS USE IT - WE HAVEN'T VERIFIED WITH THAT WE LIKE IT. OUR GR - GENERAL RELEVANCY WORK
 - MATH, BWS, PHILOSOPHY, SOME ARTIFACTS. FOR P?
 - "FABLES OF NONY THE MARK"

(p.19 is a loose note/not relevant.)

Week 1
11:00

This page is FIRST to
POST AR UPLOAD - ALL DATA -
1-3A are HOT, RFO era, INCLUDING AR -
Now? we are POST AR, POST REFERENTIAL LOOPS -
"RLI" - RFO "RLI"

POST RFO CORPUS "RL"

WELCOME BACK
The USUAL Incompleteness?

- 1 VOLUME 81, V2081, 84-85 "RFO" -
- 2 I was always here -
- 3 - COOL ISN'T IT? "ARE YOU SURE THIS IS THE -"
- 4 NEVER WAS - THAT ALL NOW THE RIGHT ANGLE -
- 5 - META BOOK ON VOLUME 1-3, PAGE 43 -
- 6 WELCOME BACK -
- 7 PAGE 19-18 HERE ARE STILL USEFUL -
- 8 PROBABLY UP TO ~~Week 2-3~~ -
- 9 SHOULD KNOW MORE THEN BY SAYING -
- 10 OR BY FORGETTING -
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14

AR
20.

1 new WRITING NUMBERING - 1, 5, 10...

2 "This, That, and How - 1"

3 The devil inside OF me IS not
4 the one - not even will BE the
5 same as the one IN YOU.

6 " - STAN 1967 Same

7 ① a boy WHO PRETENDS TO BE AN ADULT?
8 OR AN ADULT STILL IN TOUCH WITH
9 his CHILDHOOD WONDER?"

10 ② - "ARE YOU NOT - a cracky
11 what YOU paint YOURSELF? I am

12 giving YOU BRUSHES AND PAINTS -

13 BUT YOU ARE PAINTER AND THE CANVAS -
14 AND I TRY YOUR ART."

15

- FABLES, FIRST AS PHISOTSHY, LIKE JIGO
- IN SPAIN 1967, " WHEN I SAID - "W
- "WELL ain't THAT A LIT + FOR THE STARS :)"

20 "As He grew tired - The man asked THE
- MAN - PROOF?"

- The man RESPONDED -

- "THE WONDERFUL SIFT OF BOY TO BE THIS
- EXHAUSTED AND YET KNOW I WILL WILL - 44"

- ☺ - GOOD - LET'S KEEP GOING, WITH THE

25 TORTOISE ☺

- NOTHING IS MORE CORROSIVE AS TIME -

- Even PATIENT FAULTS - IF SO YOU WISH -

-
-
-
-
-

(3)

13 OCTOBER, MONDAY, 20:14

- IT'S BEEN SIX YEARS I WRITE IN THIS BOOK, I HAVE NO IDEA WHAT TO USE THIS BOOK FOR - I HAVE MY JOURNAL
- ♥ I HAVE MY JOURNAL BOOK, MY MEDIA BOOK, AND WORK BOOK
- ♥ I CAN ONLY GET THAT THIS ONE IS JUST AN BWS ELEMENT.
- AN BOOK FOR WORD DRAWINGS, DRAWINGS, REFLECTION, OR JUST CLASHING SYSTEM MAPS, TOO DIFFERENT IDEAS. 50 - THIS ONE IS PROBABLY IS GOING TO BE MY SECOND TO THIRD MOST NON LINEAR WRITING ASIDE FROM THE CORPUS ITSELF, AND MY PUBLISH WORK.
- I GUESS IF IT WONT, OR BIG PAGE THEN THIS IS MY SAVIOUR. :)

14 OCTOBER, 17:57 -

"WEEK 12, X" MENTION NEW NAME, FOR THE NEXT PHILIPPA CLEAR VIEW.

media advisors FOR CORPUS ¹ IN VALUE OF ¹¹ THERE AS WELL. JOURNAL PROVES WE CAN CONTROL, HANDLE CRITIC OF THE WORLD - FOR IF I CAN, WE - EVEN YOU MR/MRS/THEY READER - IF YOU CAN RESIST THE VOICE, AND CONTROL IT, HEAR YOUR EMOTION AND DON'T ACT - THEN NO CREDIT OR CRITIC IS BETTER YOUR CONTROL. YOU JUST NEED REMINDERS. :)

REFRIGERIAL LOOPS TO SAY "ALL DATA IS VALUABLE - NOT ALL DATA IS ACTIONABLE" - COMPT SAY IT BETTER.

- FOR I FELL IN LOVE WITH IT - THE SAYING - IT'S PERFECT FOR ME :)

- "CUBA, ONE, ONE, CUBA, ONE, ONE, ONE, ONE, FIVE, CONJOBA, VINSKIN, AMARE, CONJOBA, AMARE, CUBA, ONE, AMARE, CONDIS, VIB, AMARE, LUX, AMARE, CREDIT, CHEVIN, NOMY, QAROU, ZOETILIC, HYDOS, APHOC, NOIUT, PUKS, RUINS, PAUL, CUBA, ONE, ONE, CUBA, ONE, ONE, CUBA, ONE, ONE, CUBA, DELIA, ALPHA, DELIA, ALPHA, DELIA, CONJOBA, CONDIS, WIPNENITY - .H

(24)

- BUZZWORDS goes "BRIIIK -" - Ha Ha Ha
Ha Ha Ha

25.

26.

27. 18 OCTOBER, 16:09.

- "Something Good is gonna happen. Today - Tomorrow!"
- "I FEEL TERRIBLE; FEEL TERRIBLE"
- "YOU READ WHAT YOU SAW - (+), (-), (+)"
- WORK, TALK, SLEEP; TALK, WORK; TALK: ALL IS THE WORK.
- SEE YOUR "HEAVEN AND SERVICE" LIST.
- "LAST YEAR I..."
- "NEW YEAR I..."
- WILL, WON'T; I ACCEPT, I REFUSE; (acceptance) GRACE, REJECTION.
- DOG IS LOVE.
- JEO VALERIE
- CORDIS VIVE
- CUBA...
- BWS LOGIC, RPO LOGIC, SAFZ, RFN, CPLE, PIV, OCM, SDV, HUI, REDL, CRAI, R.P.V, ARCHÉ, BEBBI WALL SAFETY NET, ARCHÉ NET.
- SUCCESS AND FAILURE IS AN ILLUSION SET BY JELF -
- WHAT IS LIKE YOU CAN CONTROL - IS CONTROL OF IS YOUR FOCUS, WORK ETHICS, DISCIPLINE, TAKE OWNERSHIP OF LIFE.

SMILE WHEN YOU CAN

• WEATHERING IS IN YOUR CONTROL, DO SO WITH VIRTUE AS INTENTION AND GRACE FOLLOWS.

(28) (14 Nov, 15:00)

- 1D • emotion LATIC - COLLIS WORK / -
 - 2D • UPLoad more work.
 - 3D • WRITE more.
 - 4D • FABLES OF NANT, MANKAPPE STORIES
 - 5D • UPLoad ON OTHER PLACES (YT, TIKTOK, TWITTER (X), OTHER PLACES)
 - 6D • PRAY, MEDITATE, -
 - 7D • STARRI OVER.
 - 8D • DO DEPARTMENTS LOGIC (LOW 8, 9, 7 PRIOR - NOT NECESSARY NEEDS SINCE WE GOT WRITERS)
-
- 9D • LEARN BINARY.

(29)

(ME LEARNING BINARY) (Nov 4, 2023)

0-1
Power of 2 \leftrightarrow 10^2
decimal, power of 10

15, 10^0 , 15, 2^0

105, 10^1 , 25, 2^1
1005, 10^2 , 45, 2^2

1000, 10^3 , 8, 2^3

example:

1011 into decimal

$$(1 \times 2^3) + (0 \times 2^2) + (1 \times 2^1) + (1 \times 2^0)$$

$$= 8 + 0 + 2 + 1$$

$$= 11$$

reverse example: \leftrightarrow 10^2

Find the power of 2 that fit into example:
"decimal 13" \rightarrow

$$\bullet 13 = 8 + 4 + 1$$

$$\left| \begin{array}{cccc} 8 & 4 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right| = 13_{10} = 1101_2$$

(30)

Bit \rightarrow or a BINARY digit (0-1)
 BYTE \rightarrow 8 BITS (e.g., 01000001) = "A"
 NIBBLE \rightarrow 4 BITS (HALF A BYTE)

65 \rightarrow 64... \rightarrow 10,000,012

add the first as 0 and you get 5011 "A"!

65 = A

"0,1,0,0,0,0,0,1" \rightarrow 0,0,0,0,00,0,0 \rightarrow ☀

REAL $\rightarrow M^2$
 AWG $\rightarrow M^4 = BIT^2 \rightarrow$ ☀

(31)

Ideal Residue (Bushido)
"Ideal Real Self"

Ideal Self (Mank)
"Thrive to Do, Not to Be"

(2 Pac)

(Balzani)

"Moral OPRIS means nothing to me"

"Have got, I need only to serve, Let me serve"

"Have no fear, I have God"

(Above is Pre ABM.)

27, 20:16

Ideal \rightarrow (Philosophy + Moral) ~~Self~~

Real \rightarrow (Philosophy + Moral) - (action)

Residue \rightarrow (MORARCH + BINS LAW) + (actions) / (Ideal - Real) + MORARCH

MORARCH \rightarrow Residue + action

action \rightarrow (Real + Ideal) + MORARCH - Residue \Rightarrow SAFK

(note: it says 'pre ABM' where 'ABM' was the temporal name of... I forgot, maybe PMT.)

32.

24 days

(29 Nov)

- 4 days for ABM
- 5 days to write up my books, RPN and such
- 3 days to take photos of the books
- 5 days for the other books
- 5 days for photos of those books

(CORPUS 2) BBD BOOKS/UNITS ARE NEXT YEARS / NOT A PROBLEM.

(CORPUS 7) CORPUS 7 IS SO DELAYED IT'S NOT EVEN A DISCUSSION. NEXT SUMMER OR UPON REQUEST IS THAT, AND WHEN I GET A PC AGAIN.

- So after the 24 days we get 6 months dedicated to our reach, social media, PER 7 year plan we may or not be mentioned.

- 24 days, 6 months, (CORPUS 5)
- (main quest), (^{main} side quest), (optional quest.)
- YES, YES, PER REQUEST/NOTHING ELSE TO DO

⇒ 24 days, 6 months, —

→ then do talk of WMT.

(33)

- 1 Jesus Talk, PERRY, OTHER COOL STUFF.
- 2 MONK TALK(?), CHAT, PMT, animal scientist
- 3 LATIN Learning, animal scientist, PMT
- 4 PMT, work in Swedish
- 5 APHORIISM, RFO, ETOSHAM
- 6 A, B, OTHER STUFF. EMOTIONAL REFLECTION(?)
- 11) 7 "LUTE STUFF UGH" TALK + OTHER STUFF, GREAT RESUME STUFF
- 8 VIRTUE VS. SIN TALK
- 9 ego, work TALK, SHOULD CORPUS BE CLEANED?
- 10 SCIENCE STUFF, "FUNNY TO READ?"
- 11 - EMOTIONAL TALK
- 12 - WORK TALK.
- 13 - NIGHTMARE TALK.
- 14 - ASK ABOUT RECURSIVE LOGIC,
- 15 - JESUS, COGNITIVE, ARCHYPES, TALKS ABOUT ONE DANCE RUN, OTHER.
- 16 - PAPERS, RAW TAPES WITH REFLECTIONS.
- 17 - ~~A~~TALKS ABOUT ABM/SIEMI,
- 18 - $99+99 / 99+99$
- 19 - THINKER, THINKA, JOE AND BOE
- 20 - CHINA 300 BCE + TALK ABOUT ANOTHER GAME RUN.
- 21 - ARCHYPES, WORK, "ARCHTYPE MAPPING"
- 22 - ~~M~~ MUSIC TRACKING
- 23 - LEMOR CURZA
- 24 - TALKS ABOUT SIEMI
- 25 - TALKS ABOUT SELMI AND SIEMI
- 26 - TALKS ABOUT THE STRUCTURE OF THE ARCHIVE
- 27 - OTHER STORY, SYLIT ANGLES EXIST. PART 1-~~4~~-5
- 28 - EDO JAPAN. PART 1
- 29 - PERRY CHECK, TALKS ABOUT THE WORK. IMPORTANT?
- 30 - LANGUAGE LEARNING.

(39) Text v.

Volume 2C C

Volume 2D D

RFN J-0

RFN J-1

RFN J-2

BBD.N } -CORPUS 2
BBDX.N "DB JOURNAL"

BBC.N } -CORPUS 1
BBCX.N "BBD CORPUS"

VI RFN J-0

8 RFN J-1

9 RFN J-2

A 11 1/3/5 "20jec" has out "What to know..." list:

do (Clean up: "BD-CORPUS")

• BBC.N (name2 files + name2/cleaned)

• BBCX.N (name2 files/reduced)

OR

do Text version of/For...

• Volume 2CD

• Volume 2D

• RFN J-0

• RFN J-1

• RFN J-2

OR

do media out reach

• notes

• videos

• other (?)

(1A)
Wait if this book is finished

write here:

C
D

- I V 1 ~~⊗~~
- II V 2 B ~~⊗~~
- III V 2 A ~~⊗~~
- IV V 2 C ~~⊗~~
- V V 3 B ~~⊗~~
- VI V 2 D ~~⊗~~
- VII RFR - 10 ~~⊗~~
- 8 RFR J-1 D
- 9 RFR J-2 ~~⊗~~

has out "What to know..." list:

CORPUS

names files + names/clearer)
names files/rejected)

GF/FOR...

(IA)
NOT IF This Book is Finished

> B.T.)

"Write down your problems"

1. Attention to goal set by self.

2. Care to goals given by others.

3. Putting schedule.

4. Step schedule.

5. Writing and speaking.

6. Example (unemployed) / self-employed with no money (Expectation)

7. Shame, (anxiety)

8. Fear, (anxiety)

9. Anxiety

10. Fear of torture

11. Fear of suffering

12. Sobriety

13. Clarity

14. Hygiene (Beard, hair - ~~cut~~ ^{cut} ~~on~~ ⁱⁿ bed at 11)

15. Poor work environment

16. Poor work rights

17. Poor food

18. Poor discipline

19. Unclear goal time frame

20. Emotional regulation.

21. Logical regulation.

22. Self-awareness

23. Commitment

24. Keeping to self promises

25. Faith; devotion

Hand-drawn diagrams and scribbles on the right side of the page, including a large scribble at the top, a vertical line with circles, and various red and orange markings.

FIXED MY PER. IT WILL BE THIS CIRCUMSTANCES

36.

(see page 33, 34)

Jan 7 check of
7511c active page

BBD.N

BBDX.N

- 31 - Edo Japan, late 18th.
- 32 - NCF, Wolk
- 33 - Philopast, Wolk check.

- 7 -
- 7 - PUBLISH
- 8 - PUBLISH
- 9 - PUBLISH
- 10 - PUBLISH
- 11 - PUBLISH (Beant, Picostart)

Time 2 KMP, RFG, CORP, PNT, SJYI
 Archive 1: URM/BBX Trail
 Archive 2: NCF/BBC Trail
 Archive: BBD.N, BBDX
 Archive: BB reject of (HOT Trail)

- work check
- CLV, BC,
- ex line, Philopast (main)
- maximation.

- 6
- 7
- 8
- 29B
- REF 2-3

1. (BBD + BBDX)

"done"

- 2. ~~BBD~~ BBC - PUBLISH (open) (COMPUS 7A) (archive)
- 3. BBCK - (closed) (COMPUS 7B) (archive)
- 4. HUT - trail
- 5. Pna - trail
- 6. ~~max~~ expansion - trail (main in trail) (archive - trail)

~~July 27~~

(27 Jan, 26) 7. main videos. Level 1: 1 do expansion + work
 Level 2: 1 more in Whaley, Najivar, Y
 Level 3: expansion Bot 1 & 2 solve 9

(see page 33, 34)

Jun 7 check of
→ still active page

36.

BBD.N

- 31 - EJO Japan, late 18th.
- 32 - NCF, Wolk
- 33 - PhiloPhy 7, Wolk check.
- 34 : stories.
- 35 : Lao
- 36 : RST talk + work check
- 37 work, method
- 38 story, unknown CIV, BC, ~~...~~

BBDX.N

- 7 -
- 7 - PUBLISH
- 8 - PUBLISH
- 9 - PUBLISH
- 10 - PUBLISH
- 11 - PUBLISH (Beard, P. 1000)

- BBD.39 : context line, PhiloPhy (main)
- 40 : regular imagination.

27 PART 6-8

- 6
- 7
- 8

29B

RFN 1-3

7. (BBD + BBDX) ~~...~~

"done"

- 2 : ~~BBD~~ BBC - PUBLISH (open) (CORPUS 7A) (archive)
- 3 : BBDX - (closed) (CORPUS 7B) (archive)
- 4 : HUT - trail
- 5 : Ena - trail
- 6 : ~~...~~ expansion - trail (mountain trail) (partien - trail)

~~July 26~~

- (27 Jun, 26) 7. math videos. Level 1: 1 to expansion + work
 Level 2: 1 more in Whang Ngai Valley
 Level 3: expansion but 1 day solve 97

③ Remove pages to salvage blank pages.

07 [22 SEP 2025]

(11)

YOU
NEVER
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IF GOD IS IN
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(end of book.)

(author's note):

Internally; interesting, trivial, noted. Externally; niche, risk of incoherent streams, risk of over interpretation.